

Assessing Climate and Seismic Vulnerability of the Yeni Mosque in Mytilene, Lesvos

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ABSTRACT

This research evaluates the multi-hazard exposure of the Yeni Mosque (Mytilene) to climate change and seismic activity, integrating historical and contextual documentation with downscaled climate projections (DEAR-Clima; RCP4.5/8.5). A Heritage Hazard Index (HHI) framework is used to establish qualitative hazard classifications for two forthcoming 30-year intervals (2031-2060 and 2071-2100). The existing pathology, which includes the deterioration of coatings, decay of mortar, and corrosion of metallic tie rods, is recorded, and non-destructive testing (NDT), along with monitoring and reconstruction of the dome, are suggested as a protective strategy, followed by a subsequent risk “re-assessment” after the interventions.

Keywords: Climate change, Heritage Hazard Index (HHI), Risk analysis, Non-destructive testing (NDT), Climate and seismic vulnerability, Yeni Mosque (Mytilene)

1. Climate Change

Climate change, a phenomenon defined as "a change of climate which is attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which is in addition to natural climate variability observed over comparable periods" (UNFCCC, 1992). This distinction between "climate change" which alters the composition of the atmosphere and is due to human activities, and "climate variability" which is due to natural causes, is crucial. The ongoing climate change is a scientific concept and a reality expected to directly impact people, their environment, ecosystems, and protected areas worldwide (UNESCO World Heritage Center, 2007). The recent IPCC Report (IPCC, 2021) points out, with great certainty, that global warming is progressing faster than estimated in previous research. The 20th century witnessed the most significant rise in global temperatures observed over the past millennium. As a result of global warming, additional changes in climate data are expected (UNESCO World Heritage Center, 2007), including:

- 44 • Changes in the frequency and intensity of rainfall
- 45 • Changes in atmospheric humidity and wind patterns
- 46 • Changes in the frequency, intensity and seasonality of extreme events (floods, storms,
- 47 tropical cyclones, droughts, fires, snow cover)
- 48 • Sea level rise and coastal erosion (due to glacier retreat, ice melt)
- 49 • Increased carbon dioxide levels in the atmosphere and increased ocean acidification due
- 50 to dissolved carbon dioxide in water

51 If the predictions are confirmed in the future, the impacts will damage the world's cultural heritage
 52 (UNESCO World Heritage Center, 2007).
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54 1.1 Understanding Changes in Climate Indicators and Their Impacts on Monuments

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 56 Archaeological sites and monuments, historic buildings, movable objects, collections, and
 57 intangible heritage are cultural heritage properties that are subject to interactions with their
 58 environment. Climate change is a potential threat to their state of preservation as it exacerbates
 59 the expected rates of deterioration or contributes to the emergence of new ones. The physical,
 60 chemical and biological deterioration mechanisms may degrade the materials or even the entire
 61 structure of a monument (Kapsomenakis et al., 2023a; Sesana et al., 2021).
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64 **Table 1.** - Impacts of climatic indicators on monumental structures (Sesana et al.)
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Climate indicators	Climate change risk	Impacts on monuments
Temperature	Extreme heat waves, snow loading, ice storms, wet frost events	Thermal stress and deterioration on structural surfaces
Rainfall patterns	Increased intensity and frequency, floods	Salt crystallisation, sub-florescences, biological infestation, breakdown of hygroscopic materials, changes in subsoil and soil chemistry
Wind and wind-driven rain	Direction and speed	Particles of pollutants, sand, and salts may cause friction and damage to the surfaces, static and dynamic loading, and water penetration into porous materials
Sea level rise	Coastal erosion, seawater intrusion into nearby monuments	Erosion in structural materials, destabilisation of the ground
Air pollution	Gases, aerosols, acid rain	Black crusting on surfaces, degradation of carbonate stones (karst effect), corrosion of metals

66 67 68 1.2 Deterioration Processes of Building Materials

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 70 Deterioration is any chemical, electrochemical, mechanical and biological process of
 71 deterioration of the surface of materials (external or internal) that leads to material loss and applies
 72 to all building materials (stones, marbles, metals and more).

Table 2. - Wear processes in different building materials

Building materials	Deterioration processes/factors	Impacts on materials
Decay of stones	Freeze-thaw cycles	Internal stresses and damage (cracking, flaking and detachments of parts)
	Salt crystallisation	Cracking, splitting, and flaking in the materials and surfaces
	Biological infestation	Destructive action, aesthetic deterioration
Decay of mortars	Salt crystallisation	Cracks, disintegration, detachments
	Biological infestation	Destructive action, aesthetic deterioration
Corrosion of metals	Temperature	Chemical reactions that cause corrosion, thermal stresses, cracks, corrosion
	Precipitation and relative humidity	Corrosion, dissolution of the metal
	Salts	Corrosion
Decay of timber	Moisture	Swelling, deformation, distortion Shrinks, cracks, splits
	Biological infestation	Losses of wood

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76 1.3 Future Scenarios of Climate Change

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78 Computational climate models are numerical models that use equations and computational
79 algorithms to simulate the Earth's climate system, developed by the Intergovernmental Panel on
80 Climate Change (IPCC). It is a framework that describes scenarios and pathways based on an
81 assumed sequence or progression of events and with assumptions about socioeconomic
82 developments, climate-related policies, and climate change. They are tools used by scientists to
83 simulate and predict both regional and global future climates, equations based on the basic laws
84 of physics, fluid motion, and chemistry. Simply stated, they are computer programs that simulate
85 the way our planet's climate works, both now and in the future.

86 These models consider:

- 87 • the atmosphere (winds, temperature, precipitation, clouds),
- 88 • the oceans (currents, water temperature),
- 89 • The ice (sea and land ice),
- 90 • The land (vegetation cover, soil), and
- 91 • the interaction between these systems

92 Through computational climate models, it is possible to make projections into the future,
93 considering different greenhouse gas emission "scenarios". Scientists, through computational
94 climate modelling, use pre-defined 'scenarios' that describe how humanity might evolve in terms
95 of energy, population, technology and emissions. The best known are RCPs (Representative
96 Concentration Pathways) and the newer SSPs (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways).

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98 Representative Concentration Pathways

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100 The RCPs are scenarios developed to model different climate futures, based on the projected
101 concentrations of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere that will increase total radiation by 2100.
102 The RCPs are:

- 103 • RCP2.6 -Very low emissions
- 104 • RCP4.5 - Stabilization scenario
- 105 • RCP6.0 – Intermediate
- 106 • RCP8.5 - High emissions

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108 **Figure 1.** - Emission scenarios of GHGs and the resulting radiative forcing levels for RCPs (source: IPCC, 2014)

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110 **Shared Socioeconomic Pathways**

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112 The SSPs are scenarios describing a different "storyline" for possible societal and economic
 113 developments until 2100. They aim to predict how different socio-economic conditions will affect
 114 greenhouse gas emissions and the ability of societies to adapt to environmental change. There
 115 are five main scenarios (SSP1 to SSP5), ranging from a sustainable low-emission pathway (SSP1)
 116 to a future of strong economic growth with fossil fuel dependence (SSP5).

117 This established framework of future climate scenarios serves as a foundation for scientists
 118 and policymakers to strategise and respond to climate change.

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121 **Figure 2.** - Summary of the assumptions of SSPs (source: Waldhoff & Edmonds, 2013)

Relationship Between SSPs and RCPs

The SSPs and RCPs are interlinked, as socio-economic conditions shape emission trajectories at the global level. The scientific community can explore a range of possible future climate outcomes by combining all of the above data. In the IPCC 6th Assessment Report, the SSPs and the approximate global effective radiative forcing (ERF) up to 2100 were combined, creating the new categories SSP1-1.9, SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5, representing scenarios with:

- SSP1-1.9 and SSP1-2.6: Very low or low GHG and CO₂ emissions, falling to net zero around or after 2050, alongside a range of net harmful CO₂ emission levels
- SSP2-4.5: Medium GHG and CO₂ emissions remaining at the same levels as today until mid-century
- SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5Q High and very high GHG and CO₂ emissions. Almost doubling from current levels by 2050 (SSP5-8.5) and by 2100 (SSP3-7.0). The different gas emissions also affect the rate of global temperature increase.

Figure 3. - Future annual emissions for the five different scenarios (source: IPCC, 2014)

1.4 Global Climate Change Predictions

As GHG emissions continue, further warming is expected to occur. At the same time, long-term changes in climate system indicators are expected, resulting in irreversible and severe impacts on ecosystems and human populations. There is a strong possibility that more frequent and longer-lasting heat waves will occur, that extreme precipitation events will become more intense and frequent in many areas, that the oceans will continue to warm and acidify, and that global average sea levels will rise. To mitigate and reduce the risks arising from climate change, sustained reductions in GHG emissions and adaptation to a changing climate are needed. According to the scientific community, however, significant changes in climate patterns will occur (temperature increase, changes in precipitation, floods, droughts, etc.) even if carbon dioxide emissions are significantly reduced in the coming years (UNESCO World Heritage Center, 2007). Under all emission scenarios considered, global surface temperatures will continue to rise until the mid-21st century. If CO₂ and other GHG emissions do not increase significantly in the coming decades, global warming will exceed by 1.5 - 2°C. According to the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report, simulations of future climate change cover the time horizons for the near-term (2021-2040), mid-term (2041-2060), and long-term (2081-2100). The future projections are evaluated against the pre-industrial period 1850-1900 and the recent past 1995-2014.

158 The following picture shows the simulated annual global surface temperature change relative
 159 to 1850–1900, and the percentage precipitation change, at global warming levels of 1.5°C, 2°C
 160 and 4 degrees Celsius.
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Figure 4. - Simulation of temperature increasing and annual mean precipitation changes depending on the temperature rise (source: IPCC, 2021)

166 The table shows that in the near term, 2021-2040, the average temperature increase
 167 ranges from 1.5-1.6 degrees Celsius, depending on the scenario, in the mid-term, 2041-2060,
 168 from 1.6-2.4, and in the long term, 2081-2100, from 1.4 - 4.4
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Table 3. - Future increase of global temperature under five different scenarios (source: IPCC, 2021)

Scenarios	Increase in Global Surface Temperature					
	Near-term 2021-2040		Mid-term 2041-2060		Long-term 2081-2100	
	Temperature rise range (°C)	Mean	Temperature rise range (°C)	Mean	Temperature rise range (°C)	Mean
SSP1-1.9	1.2 - 1.7	1.5	1.2 - 2.0	1.6	1.0 - 1.8	1.4
SSP1-2.6	1.2 - 1.8	1.5	1.3 - 2.2	1.7	1.3 - 2.4	1.8
SSP2-4.5	1.2 - 1.8	1.5	1.6 - 2.5	2.0	2.1 - 3.5	2.7
SSP3-7.0	1.2 - 1.8	1.5	1.7 - 2.6	2.1	2.8 - 4.6	3.6
SSP5-8.5	1.2 - 1.9	1.6	1.9 - 3.0	2.4	3.3 - 5.7	4.4

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2. Case study-Yeni Mosque in Mytilene of Lesvos Island

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The Yeni Mosque was built during the Ottoman Empire, in 1825 AD, by the Nazir of Mytilene, Moustafa Aga Kouloxizi; its construction was carried out by Greek craftsmen, combining Ottoman and Byzantine elements and is a very interesting building for the city from an aesthetic and architectural point of view. It is the largest Muslim Mosque in the capital of Lesvos Island, Mytilini, and is a reference point of the 18th and 19th centuries on the island. It belonged to the Muslim community of Mytilene and is one of the most characteristic mosques, representative of its time and of the Islamic art that developed on Greek soil. In 1951, the City Council removed the dome because it reminded of the then-recent period of Turkish rule.

Using an RTK Drone, a three-dimensional (3-D) digital model of the monument was created, to observe and approach the monument in its entirety. A three-dimensional digital model of a monument can be a valuable tool for its preservation, as it allows the accurate documentation of the state of the monument at a specific point in time.

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Figure 5. - Northeast and Southwestern view of the monument

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Figure 6. - The Yeni Mosque of Mytilene and the absence of the dome

192 **2.1 Construction technology of the monument**

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In plan, the typology of the monument is a cross inscribed in a rectangular parallelogram, with a drum and a dome supported by four columns connected by arches. The whole construction is of Turkish-Byzantine style, stone-built, and tile-covered.

The surviving part of the minaret (once over 30 meters high) is made of carved limestone and rises to 14 m on the northwestern face of the mosque.

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Figure 7. - Design floor plan of Yeni Çami (left) and image from the digital 3D model (right)

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Figure 8. - The truncated minaret

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All the masonry was stone with lime mortar, with extensive use of bricks, wooden reinforcement and abundant metal tie-rods. The building stones for the construction of the monument are derived from the natural rocks of the area, which are basic and ultrabasic igneous rocks

Since the removal of the dome, the structure has remained exposed, amplifying the effects of weathering. Restoration interventions in 2001 stabilised some elements, but key vulnerabilities still suffer degradation.

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Figure 9. - North and South sides

Figure 10. - Metal tie-rods

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2.2 Historical Climate Data of Mytilene (1979-2024)

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In cooperation with Meteoblue and the history+ platform, obtaining historical climate data from 1940 to 2024 for Mytilene was possible.

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The following graph shows the anomaly of temperature and humidity for each month from 1979-2023 compared to the 30-year climate average for 1980-2010. What can be seen is that months with a warmer climate are shown in red, while months with a colder climate are shown in blue. As can be seen, there is an increase in warmer months, which represents global warming and climate change. Similarly, in the rainfall graph, the anomaly is whether each month had less or more rainfall compared to the 30 years mentioned above. Thus, the wetter months are shown in green, while the drier months are shown in brown. Therefore, there is an increase in both temperature and precipitation patterns.

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Figure 11. - Temperature and precipitation anomaly from 1979 to 2023 (source: Meteoblue)

234 **2.3 Seismicity of Lesvos**

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Lesvos, located in one of the most earthquake-prone regions of Greece, has a complex fault pattern that is affected by several active faults in the region, either on land or at sea (Zouros et al., 2011). Six major faults are noted. At the same time, it is affected by the Anatolian Fault.

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Figure 12. - Lesvos' faults (source: Chatzipetros et al., 2013)

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Figure 13. - Map of active geodynamics of Eastern Mediterranean (source: Papazachos V., 2003)

244 According to Eurocode 8, Lesvos is ranked in zone 2, where the seismic acceleration factor
 245 equal to 0.24.

246 From 1883 to 2022, more than 158 solid or weak earthquakes have been recorded, ranging
 247 from 4.1 to 7.2 R, with the strongest one occurring in 1867 with 7 R degrees, where it significantly
 248 destroyed the city of Mytilene.
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 251 **Figure 14.** - Seismicity zones of Greece (EC-8). Lesvos is ranked in zone 2, where the seismic acceleration factor
 252 is equal to 0.24 (source: OASP)

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YEAR	EPICENTER NEAR	DISTANCE (km)	MAGNITUDE ML	PGA(g) ¹	PGA(g) ²	PGA(g) ³	SOIL TYPE	S (EC-8)	S _r (EC-8)	a _{eff} (g) ⁽¹⁾
1383	Kaloni	28.2	6.8	0.134	0.155	0.164	B	1.2	1.0	0.107
1636	Kaloni	28.2	6.2	0.072	0.095	0.086	B	1.2	1.0	0.058
1688	Yenise	104.7	6.6	0.022	0.026	0.033	B	1.2	1.0	0.018
1672	Tenedos	89.0	7.0	0.042	0.045	0.061	B	1.2	1.0	0.033
1737	Etili	88.6	7.2	0.051	0.054	0.076	B	1.2	1.0	0.041
1809	Tenedos	89.0	6.9	0.037	0.042	0.055	B	1.2	1.0	0.030
1826	Etili	88.6	6.6	0.028	0.033	0.040	B	1.2	1.0	0.022
1845	Kaloni	28.2	6.7	0.121	0.143	0.147	B	1.2	1.0	0.097
1865	Edremit	42.7	6.6	0.068	0.083	0.087	B	1.2	1.0	0.054
1867	Kaloni	28.2	7.0	0.165	0.183	0.204	B	1.2	1.0	0.132
1889	Kaloni	28.2	6.8	0.134	0.155	0.164	B	1.2	1.0	0.107
1944	Edremit	42.7	6.9	0.092	0.106	0.120	B	1.2	1.0	0.074
1953	Yenise	104.7	7.4	0.051	0.050	0.078	B	1.2	1.0	0.041
2014	S. Lesvos	34.9	4.6	0.011	0.020	0.012	B	1.2	1.0	0.009
2015	N. Lesvos	35.0	4.2	0.007	0.015	0.008	B	1.2	1.0	0.006
2015	Karaburun	69.6	4.0	0.003	0.005	0.003	B	1.2	1.0	0.002
2016	Foça	59.9	4.4	0.005	0.009	0.006	B	1.2	1.0	0.004
2017	Kizilkeçili	57.7	4.4	0.005	0.009	0.006	B	1.2	1.0	0.004
2017	Tuzla	67.5	5.0	0.007	0.013	0.009	B	1.2	1.0	0.006
2017	S. Lesvos	33.4	4.9	0.015	0.027	0.018	B	1.2	1.0	0.012
2017	S. Lesvos	47.8	4.2	0.005	0.010	0.006	B	1.2	1.0	0.004
2018	S. Lesvos	29.3	4.0	0.007	0.015	0.008	B	1.2	1.0	0.006
2021	S. Lesvos	48.8	4.1	0.004	0.009	0.005	B	1.2	1.0	0.003
2022	Çesme	106.4	4.4	0.002	0.004	0.003	B	1.2	1.0	0.002

(¹) Scariatoudis (2003), (²) Rinaldis (1998), (³) Modified Mercalli Intensity: Koliopoulos (1998)

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Figure 15. - Strong historic earthquake events at Lesvos Island

256 **2.4 Current State of Preservation/Pathology**

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The most significant damage to the Yeni Mosque occurred in 1951, following the removal of the dome, where the monument was left exposed to time and weather conditions that led to extensive loss of interior decoration. Today, the monument, even though it is still uncovered, despite the changes in climatic conditions and the intense seismicity of the area, is in a good state of preservation, to which some of the conservation interventions carried out in 2001 have partially contributed.

The main damages observed on the monument are an extensive loss of interior decoration, local inadequacies and mortar losses on the masonry, losses and damages of coatings on columns, and major cracks at column bases.

The following pairs of photos show before and after the loss of coatings from 2000 to 2024.

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Figure 16. - Southeastern column before and after coating loss (the left photo was taken between 1992-2000, and the right photo was taken in 2024)

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Figure 17. - Coating losses at the base of a column (the left photo was taken between 1992-2000, and the right photo was taken in 2024)

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Figure 18. - Damage on the base of a column and semi-column

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All the metallic elements and the tractors in the upper part of the building show severe corrosion. A significant issue is the cracks that formed on the structure from the swelling of metals. It is visible in the area around metal keys where the tractors penetrate, causing stresses in the structural materials, weakening their cohesion. Their swelling due to corrosion creates stresses in the structural materials, weakening their cohesion.

The tractors of the north arch in the central block are pretty battered, where cracks and curvature observed. Moreover, it is observed that a metal ring on the NW column has broken and fallen, leaving the joint of the two marble drums uncovered.

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Figure 19. – Corroded metal connector

Figure 20. – Damaged metal tractors

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Figure 22. – (left) Cracks due to swelling of metal

Figure 21. – (right) Broken metal ring

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3. Projected evolution of the structural pathology of the Yeni Mosque until 2100

3.1 Climate predictions for Mytilene

299 The climate forecast data for the area where the Yeni Mosque is located was obtained from
300 the web-based Data Extraction Application for Regional Climate (DEAR-Clima), using the
301 monument's exact coordinates.

302 DEAR-Clima is an interactive tool that provides time series data for climate indicators,
303 illustrating climate changes from 1950 to 2100. The projections are based on simulations of high
304 horizontal resolution Regional Climate Models (RCMs) driven by Global Climate Models (GCMs)
305 of the Coordinated Regional Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) research project. EURO-
306 CODEX is the application domain, and the simulations cover Europe, the Mediterranean, and part
307 of northern Africa.

308 The derived data project the historical period 1950-2004 and the future period from 2006-2100
309 for the three greenhouse gas emission scenarios: rcp2.6, rcp4.5 and rcp8.5. However, for the case
310 of Yeni Mosque, the data for the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios will be considered.
311

312 Temperature

313 Looking at the following graph, there is a clear upward trend for both the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5
314 scenarios. Notably, both scenarios show a linear upward trend until about 2040. While for RCP4.5,
315 the trend continues smoothly, for RCP8.5, the trend forms a stronger upward trend until 2100.

316

317 **Figure 23.** - Annual mean temperature chart for RCP4.5 (orange line) and RCP8.5 (red line) for the period 1950-
318 2100 (source: DEAR-Clima)

319 Daily data from DEAR-Clima were obtained and processed to calculate the number of days
320 with temperatures above 37 °C. In the following graph, the increase in the number of days with
321 extreme temperatures for the future is clearly shown. More specifically, for the period 2031-2060,
322 200 days/30yr are noted in RCP4.5 with an increase of 104% compared to the historical period
323 with 98 days/30yr, while 251 days/30yr are noted in RCP8.5 with an increase of 156%. Similarly,
324 for the period 2071-2100, RCP4.5 has 363 days/30yr with an increase of 270%, and RCP8.5 has
325 740 days with an increase of 655%.

326

327 **Figure 24.** - Graph of the mean number of days with temperature above 37 °C for the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5
 328 scenarios, covering the historical and future period in a 30-year range

329 The following graph shows a continuous linear decrease in days with continuous low
 330 temperatures. More specifically, for RCP4.5, there appears to be a smoother decline until 2100,
 331 while for RCP8.5, there is a steeper decline from about 2060 onwards.

332

333 **Figure 25.** - Annual graph of continuous frost days for RCP4.5 (orange line) and RCP8.5 (red line) for the period
 334 1950-2100 (source: DEAR-Clima)

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336 The data used in this analysis, obtained from the reputable source DEAR-Clima, was
 337 processed to calculate the number of days with temperatures below 0 °C. The following graph
 338 shows a significant decrease in frost days. Specifically, for 2031-2060, 287 days/30yr are noted in
 339 RCP4.5 with a decrease of -38% compared to the historical period with 468 days/30yr, while 249
 340 days/30yr are noted in RCP8.5 with a decrease of -47%. Similarly, for 2071-2100, RCP4.5 has
 341 147 days/30yr with a -69% decrease, and RCP8.5 has 106 days with a -77% decrease.

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343 **Figure 26.** - Graph of the mean number of days with temperature below 0 °C for the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5
 344 scenarios, covering the historical and future period in a 30-year range

345 **Precipitation**

346 In the following diagram, for both RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios, precipitation patterns show
 347 a neutral linear trend that does not show strong fluctuations until 2100. However, from the daily
 348 value data obtained and processed by DEAR-Clima, a better picture emerges of the changes in
 349 the number of days with precipitation that exceeds the 99th percentile.

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351 **Figure 27.** - Annual diagram where precipitation exceeds the 99th percentile for RCP4.5 (orange line) and
 352 RCP8.5 (red line) for the period 1950-2100 (source: DEAR-Clima)

353 In the following graph, some irregular variations are shown for the patterns of extreme rainfall
 354 in the future. Specifically, for 2031-2060, 434 days/30yr are noted in RCP4.5 with a 0.9% decrease
 355 compared to the historical period with 438 days/30yr, while 470 days/30yr are noted in RCP8.5
 356 with a 7% increase. Similarly, for 2071-2100, RCP4.5 has 489 days/30yr with an increase of 12%,
 357 and RCP8.5 has 456 days with an increase of 4%. In conclusion, it appears that for RCP4.5, a
 358 slight decrease in the number of days with extreme precipitation is projected for 2031-2060, but
 359 increases for 2071-2100. In contrast, for RCP8.5, an increase in the number of days is projected
 360 for 2031-2060, while decreasing for 2071-2100.
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Figure 28. - Mean number of days where precipitation exceeds the 99th percentile for the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios, covering the historical and future period in a 30-year range

3.2 Risk analysis

Anthropogenic global warming, the resulting extreme events, and seismic activity are increasing the rate of threats and risks to most cultural heritage sites in the Mediterranean (where Lesvos is located), ranked among the most vulnerable areas to climate change in the coming decades (Kapsomenakis et al., 2023).

The volatile nature of climate risks, uncertain modelling of future climate change, and other socio-economic parameters increase the complexity of the risk analysis process. Risk-based structural design and evaluation methods are applied to examine and understand the consequences of an overall structural failure, more so than the potential failures of individual members.

Risk assessment and risk management are the two critical components of risk analysis. When assessing risks, four parameters must be considered:

- Hazard identification
- Assessment of the magnitude of the risk
- Structural vulnerability assessment - analysis of the structural response to potential failures from a hazard or combination of hazards
- Evaluation of the consequences of failure (losses)

Risks may arise from physical deterioration during the use of a monument, malicious or accidental man-made activities, environmental/climatic conditions and extreme events. Considering and analysing the above information leads to risk management, where multidisciplinary teams make decisions to mitigate the risks (Ghosn et al., 2019).

To assess the risks to which the Yeni Mosque is exposed, the methodology presented in the work of Kapsomenakis et al., 2023 was followed, in which a multi-hazard risk assessment was carried out for 244 natural and cultural heritage sites of UNESCO for the Mediterranean region. The research covers the period 1971-2100, and the simulations are for the IPCC emission scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5.

The Heritage Hazard Index (HHI), calculated from Equation 1, estimates the overall threat from anthropogenic climate change and seismicity synergy.

$$(1) \quad HHI = CCCHaz + \sqrt{(CCHaz) \times (SHaz)}$$

- where CCTHaz = Σ [Climate Change Hazards Sub-indices]
A sum of all indicators: extreme heat hazard (EHHaz), frost hazard (FHaz), extreme precipitation hazard (EPHaz), aridity hazard (AHaz) and coastal flooding hazard (CFHaz), representing the anthropogenic risks of climate change

- where SHaz = seismic hazard
Represents the values of seismic hazard (SHaz) according to the extracted peak ground acceleration (PGA)

406 Calculation of CCCTHaz

407 To assess the possible man-made climatic hazards threatening the Yeni Çami, five extreme
408 climate indices (1-5) were analysed, whose values were derived from the climate projections data
409 for Mytilene, and represent the changes in the extreme climate indices for the two 30-year future
410 periods 2031-2060 and 2071-2100, relevant to the reference 30-year period 1975-2004, under
411 scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. Then, calculated with the synergy of the seismicity of Lesvos and
412 the topography. Below, the hazard indicators to be analysed are listed (Kapsomenakis et al., 2023):

1. **TX37** (days/year) - Number of days per year with extreme hot days and, more specifically, days with maximum air temperature above 37 °C.
2. **PR99** (days/year) - Number of days exceeding the historical 99th-percentile daily rainfall
3. **TN0** (days/year) - Number of days per year with night frost, noting minimum temperature below 0
4. **AI (-)** - Index of the aridity of the climate in a region. The index is calculated from the ratio between precipitation and potential evapotranspiration. To calculate the AI, average monthly values for temperature at 2m (Tm) and precipitation (Pm) are used
5. **Sea Level Rise (SLR)** - is calculated for monuments up to 3km from the sea and elevation less or equal to 20m and refers to the risk of possible, future sea level rise (estimated as a percentage).

424 To assess the synergistic effect of seismic activity, the expected peak ground acceleration
425 (**PGA**) is selected as an indicator of seismic hazard.

426 Risk Analysis – Results

429 According to Kapsomenakis et al., 2023, the range of values of the qualitative hazard
430 characterisation of the HHI is:

- 0-4 Low
- 4-8 Moderate
- 8-12 High
- 12-16 Extreme

436

437 **Table 4.** - Qualitative characterisation of hazard for Yeni Mosque under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios

30-year periods	Scenario	CCCTHaz	SHaz	HHI	Qualitative characterisation of hazard
2031-2060	RCP4.5	8	3	12,90	Extreme
	RCP8.5	9	3	14,20	Extreme
2071-2100	RCP4.5	10	3	15,48	Extreme
	RCP8.5	9	3	14,20	Extreme

438

439 The calculations showed that the relative climate impacts on the Yeni Mosque will worsen
440 to an extreme degree in the future under the two scenarios. However, this is not an absolute
441 value, as the effect of climate change is relative to the current state of monument preservation.
442 The monument is preserved in good condition, and the current climate impact is minor.

443 In addition, it is noted that the risk of sea level rise has been taken into account in the
444 analysis of the climate indicators, but this does not affect the monument, as it is located about
445 240 m from the coast, and the water is not expected to reach it.

446 Therefore, although the results magnified the climate impact to a high degree, less impact
447 on the monument is expected.
448

449 **4. Recommended Actions for the Future**

450 **4.1. Diagnostic methods and intervention measures**

451

452 **Diagnostic methods**

453

454 A. In situ – Non-Destructive Testing (NDT)

455 Non-destructive diagnostic methods are extremely important for assessing the condition of a
456 monument without damaging it. The appropriate method choice depends on the material's nature,
457 the type of problems sought and the accuracy of the results required. These methods lead to
458 analysing and recording the condition of materials and structures to make appropriate decisions
459 on conservation and restoration (Penelis, 2020).

460 i. Further estimation of natural and mechanical properties

- 461 • Hammer test

462 ii. Assessment of the structure's state of preservation

- 463 • Acoustic emission
- 464 • Ultrasound
- 465 • Thermography

466

467 B. Basic monitoring

468 Structural health monitoring (SHM) is a process in which a structure can be observed over time
469 through an automated monitoring system that takes periodically sampled measurements.
470 Instrumental monitoring of the monument allows for detecting any possible structural changes,
471 which can be immediately addressed, and measures can be taken to better protect the monument.
472 Various factors can affect structural health, such as natural deterioration of structural materials
473 (possibly premature), structural loads, climatic conditions, extreme events, and earthquakes. Since
474 all of the above parameters are variable, monitoring a structure's response is necessary to detect
475 deterioration continuously (Chen & Ni, 2018). For reliable structural health assessment, advanced
476 sensors detect damage that provides real-time monitoring and are placed at critical points of a
477 structure. In addition, sensors should be selected according to the measured quantities deemed
478 necessary to be monitored for each case study individually (Chen & Ni, 2018).

- 479 • Structural response and geometry configuration (strain gages, accelerometers, biaxial
480 tiltmeters, distance meters)
- 481 • Environmental quantities (temperature, humidity, wind)

482 ■ Accelerometres ■ Biaxial tiltmeters ■ Distance metres □ Temperature and humidity

483 **Figure 29.** - Indicative locations of sensors for continuous monitoring of the monument's health

485 After a deeper reading and decoding of the state of preservation of both the structural materials
 486 and the construction as a unit, the mechanisms of deterioration, and structural response, it is finally
 487 proposed to repeat the study of the monument to make better decisions on its conservation and
 488 reconsider the reconstruction of the dome that will significantly contribute to its protection.

489 **Intervention measures**

- 490
 491 A. Reconstruction of the dome
 492 B. Typical periodic conservation of the structural and the non-structural parts of the
 493 monument
 494

495
 496 **4.2 Reconsidering RISK after the proposed interventions**

497
 498 Concerning climatic deterioration, the reconstruction of the dome will serve as a natural barrier
 499 against the impacts of climate change, such as humidity, sudden temperature changes and
 500 radiation, contributing to the stabilisation of the interior microclimate and the reduction of material
 501 deterioration. At the same time, a properly designed dome can enhance the cohesion of the
 502 structure, improve the seismic behaviour of the monument by minimising relative movements
 503 within the structure.

504 To avoid distorting the risk analysis framework applied in the research, the hazard is artificially
 505 minimised to reflect (in a simplified manner) the decreased vulnerability due to the implemented
 506 measures. Consequently, when reassessing the risk following the dome's reconstruction, the
 507 interventions do **not** change the hazard; instead, they affect vulnerability/capacity, thereby
 508 influencing the overall risk.

509 **Table 5.** - Qualitative characterisation of hazard for Yeni Mosque under the two scenarios, after the intervention
 510 measures

30-year periods	Scenario	CCCTHaz	SHaz	HHI	Qualitative characterisation of hazard
2031-2060	RCP4.5	1	2	2,41	Low
	RCP8.5	2	2	4	Low
2071-2100	RCP4.5	1	2	2,41	Low
	RCP8.5	2	2	4	Low

511 **Conclusions**

512
513 In this research, the importance of assessing the climatic effects on monumental structures is
514 highlighted.

515 The use of climate projections for the near future, combined with relevant risk assessment
516 methodologies, constitutes a powerful tool for prioritisation, informed decision-making, and the
517 development of effective restoration strategies.

518 Additionally, the three-dimensional geometric recording of monumental structures plays a
519 crucial role in conservation efforts. It provides an accurate depiction of the current condition of a
520 structure, change detection between epochs, and damage mapping, forming the baseline for
521 identifying climatic and seismic impacts.

522 Such detailed documentation enables the precise reading of weathering patterns, structural
523 deformations, and other environmental effects, thereby supporting both diagnostics and long-term
524 monitoring.

525

526

527 **Conflict of Interest Disclosure**

528

529 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of
530 interest in relation to the content of the article.

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